

Susceptibility of Groundnut Cultivars to Secondary Storage Pest *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) in Stored Groundnut in Yola, Adamawa State

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this laboratory study was to determine how vulnerable five groundnut cultivars were to attack by the red flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). The experiment was conducted in the Department of Crop Protection at Modibbo Adama University Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria, using a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) with three replications over a three-month period. ANOVA was used to examine the data, and the treatment means were separated using the Tukeys Kramer (HSD) test with a p-value of 0.05. The study revealed that the five groundnut cultivars generated a somewhat small number of progeny, with the mean numbers for Yar-dakar, Gwandara, Yar-baino, Kampala, and Kwankwasiya being 18.35, 15.10, 12.28, 12.15, and 9.01, respectively. The developmental period of Yar-dakar, Gwandara, and Kampala were the greatest (44.0 days each) followed by Yar-baino and Kwankwasiya of 42.0 days and 40.0 days, respectively. All the cultivars were moderately resistant with susceptibility index that ranged from 4.77 - 5.74. Percentage grain damage and weight loss were highest in Yar-dakar of 33.15% and 33.66%, respectively as compared to the other varieties. This study revealed that *T. castaneum* been known as insect pest of groundnut, had the ability to attack and to breed successively in all the groundnuts cultivars. Therefore, farmers and traders are advised on choice of cultivars especially Kampala and Kwankwasiya which showed low grain damage and weight loss. Also traders are advised to devise integrated management strategies to avert these losses.

Keywords: Susceptibility; Groundnut; Cultivars; Pest; *Tribolium castaneum*

INTRODUCTION

Leguminosae, which includes the groundnut (*Arachis hypogaea* L.), is a family of significant food legumes and an oil seed crop (Beghin *et al.*, 2003). Numerous tropical, subtropical, and temperate nations around the world cultivate it (Sakhare, 2018). With a production of 45.2 Mt and a productivity of 1.77 tonnes ha⁻¹, groundnut is the world's fourth-most significant oilseed crop and the 13th-most important food crop overall (FAOSTAT, 2014). Nigeria produces 51% of the groundnuts in West Africa, making it the region's leading producer of the crop. The nation generates 39% of Africa's production

and 10% of the overall global production. The famed Kano groundnut pyramids serve as an example of how valuable groundnut was as the nation's most valued single export crop between 1956 and 1967 (Ndjeunga *et al.*, 2010). In Nigeria, it is a major crop produced in almost all northern States including Kano, Niger, Jigawa, Sokoto, Katsina, Zamfara, Kaduna, Adamawa, Bauchi, Yobe, Plateau, Kebbi, Borno, Taraba, Gombe and Nasarawa States (NAERLS, 2011).

Groundnut is a valuable food crop because of its high oil (43-55%) and protein content (25-28%), and provides vitamins and minerals for millions of households (Reddy *et al.*,

2003). For households who can afford to produce a surplus for markets, it provides scarce cash income that can be used for investing in health, children's education, and other necessities. This makes groundnut an important food security crop in both rural and urban areas (Obuo *et al.*, 2004). Despite of the numerous benefits and roles groundnut play at individual to national level in Nigeria, pod yield from farmers' field have remain low averaging 1082kg ha⁻¹ compared to 3000 kg ha⁻¹ and 3500 kg ha⁻¹, potential yield and those from developed countries, respectively (Ndjeunga *et al.*, 2010).

Groundnut is usually stored as pods (unshelled form) and in kernels (shelled form) for different uses. Storage losses of groundnut range between 10% and 15% (Ranga Rao *et al.*, 2010). Its quality and quantity is reduced during storage and post-harvest due to several insect pests (Ahmed *et al.*, 2010; Zekeri and Tijjani, 2013) though, most of the storage insect pests attack kernels, *Caryedon serratus* is the only major pest of groundnut that infests unshelled pods as well as kernels. However, other insect-pests like, pod sucking bug, *Elasmolomus sordidus*; rust-red flour beetle, *Tribolium castaneum*; the rice moth, *Corcyra cephalonica*; the merchant grain beetle, *Oryzaephilus mercator* and almond moth, *Ephestia cautella* are of minor importance where, the latter four species are secondary pests of groundnut which prefer broken or infested pods (Pandin *et al.*, 2002).

In the developing world, the high cost of chemical pesticides, and non-availability of effective formulations and efficient storage structures necessitate the need for low cost effective post-harvest insect management practices. However, while making the decisions on chemical control,

one should be aware of the economic threshold to justify the investment, level of contamination, and the operational hazards. This will further be determined based on the purpose of the product such as for oil extraction, food, seed or export (ICRISAT, 2016). Therefore, due to susceptibility of groundnut to wide range of insect pests and poor storage facilities despite its huge value and cost of production, this study is aimed to assess the infestation of shelled groundnut by *Tribolium castaneum* which has assumed primary pest status and also to ascertain the loss in weight and damage caused by this insect pest on different groundnut cultivars.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Location

The study was conducted in the Entomology Laboratory, Department of Crop Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Nigeria, under ambient laboratory conditions of temperature and relative humidity of 27 – 35°C and 55 – 75%, respectively. The Laboratory is located on geographical coordinates of latitude 9°20'49"N and longitude 12°29'41"E (Google compass, 2022).

Sources and Identification of Groundnut Cultivars

Five (5) groundnut cultivars were purchased from grain merchant in Jimeta grain market, Adamawa State and were identified by the groundnut sellers to get the local names (Plate I) and parent stock of *Tribolium castaneum* was sourced from insect colony kept in the Laboratory of Crop Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, Modibbo Adama University, Yola, Nigeria.

Plate I: Samples of groundnut cultivars found in Jimeta grain market of Adamawa State

Developing of Insects Culture

To create a laboratory colony of *Tribolium castaneum* using cleaned groundnut seeds under ambient laboratory conditions (35–40°C and 65–75% of temperature and relative humidity, respectively), the parent stock of the insect was obtained from already established colony in the entomological laboratory. This is accomplished by putting 50 pairs of unsexed adult *T. castaneum* inside a bottle of 1 liter capacity and 500 grams of cowpea seeds. After that, the bottles were covered with muslin cloth and fastened with rubber bands to prevent insects from escaping and to allow aeration. The parent stock of *T. castaneum* was taken out after oviposition had taken place for a week. The seeds containing the oviposited eggs were then kept in a laboratory condition until the F₁ progeny emerged. The F₁ progenies 1 - 3 days old from the culture were then used for the experiment (Medugu *et al.*, 2020).

Preparation of Groundnut Cultivars and Experimental Bottles

Newly harvested untreated local groundnut cultivars obtained from farmers and the experimental bottles were examined, cleaned and sterilized thermally in a hot-air oven (Hot Air Circulated Oven; OV95c) at 60°C for 1 hour to kill any pest and pathogen that might be present, and afterwards the seeds were allowed to equilibrate for 24 hours in the laboratory, while the moisture content was reduced to 12%. The above preparation was carried out prior to commencement of screening as described by Medugu, *et al.* (2020).

Experimental Procedure and Data Collection

To screen the groundnut cultivars for relative resistance to *T. castaneum*, ten pairs of unsexed (1-3 days old) adult *T. castaneum* were introduced into separate bottles containing 50 g of each groundnut cultivar weighed on a sensitive electronic balance (Electronic Compact Weighing Scale BL20001). The containers were then covered with muslin cloth and secured with rubber band to prevent escape of insects and to allow aeration. The infested groundnut seeds were left for 7 days for oviposition to take place. On day 7th day after infestation, the beetles were removed and discarded. The content of each jar was carefully returned, kept on the shelf and left undisturbed for additional 21 days. Thereafter, the bottles were examined daily to record the emergence of F₁ adults. Adult count continued until no adult(s) emerged in each jar for three consecutive days modified after Throne and Eubanks, (2002). Each treatment was replicated three times in a completely randomized design (CRD).

a) *Tribolium castaneum* adult

b) Laboratory experimental set up to study the susceptibility of 5 groundnut cultivars

According to Dobie (1977), the median developmental period (MDP) is the number of days between the middle day of the oviposition period and 50% of the F₁ adults emerging. The Dobie index of susceptibility, which was developed by Dobie (1977) and adopted by Medugu *et al.* (2021), was then employed as a criterion to divide groundnut cultivars into resistant and susceptible groups.

$$SI = \log F_1 / D \times 100.$$

Where; SI = Susceptibility Index,

Log F₁ = Log number of F₁ emerged adults, and
D = Mean length of developmental period (days).

The groundnut cultivars were then classified into susceptibility categories using the Dobie Index using the scales: >10 = extremely susceptible; >4 = highly resistant; 4 = moderately resistant; 4.1 - 6.0 = moderately susceptible; 6.1 - 8.0 = moderately susceptible; 8.1 - 10 = Susceptible; Dobie, (1974).

Loss Assessment

Losses comprise reduction in weight and damages of grains (grains with holes). At the end of the experiment all pest were removed and the remaining bulk together with the resulting frass were collected and weighed.

Grain damage

Grain damage (grains with emergence hole (s)) was determined using the method described by Abebe, *et al.* (2009) and adopted by Medugu *et al.* (2021) as a proportion of the total number of seeds sampled;

$$\text{Grain damage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Total number of damaged grains}}{\text{Total number of grains}} \times 100.$$

Weight loss

Grains were weighed using an electronic balance (Mettler Toledo AB 50) and expressed in grams, and grain weight loss was determined by count and weight method as describe by Lale (2002);

$$\text{Weight loss (\%)} = \frac{[UaN - (U + D)]}{UaN} \times 100.$$

Where; U_a = average weight of one undamaged grain;
N = total number of grains in the sample;
U = weight of undamaged fraction in the sample; and
D = weight of damaged fraction in the sample.

Statistical Analysis

Data collected were subjected to one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and differences between means were compared using Turkey-Kramer Honestly Significant difference (HSD) test at 5% probability level.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Production of Offspring and Length of *T. castaneum* Developmental Period on Five Groundnut Varieties

Table 1 lists the parameters of *T. castaneum* life history on five different groundnut substrates. The findings revealed a significant difference ($P \geq 0.05$) in the mean number of *T. castaneum* progeny generated by Yar-dakar and the other cultivars. The Kwankwasiya cultivar produced the lowest number of progeny, 9.01, and the Yar-dakar cultivar produced the largest number, 18.35. However, the number of F_1 progeny for the Gwandara, Kampala, and Yar-baino cultivars is 15.10, 12.15, and 12.85, respectively (Table 1). In contrast to Shivalingaswamy and Balasubramanian's (1992) findings, which indicated a higher mean number of adults emerging from various groundnut types of 49.0 (JL-24), this conclusion is different.

The length of developmental period of *T. castaneum* in five groundnut cultivars is not significantly different from each other ($p < 0.05$). The longest developmental period was recorded in Yar-dakar, Gwandara and Kampala (44 days each) followed by Yar-baino of 42 days. The shorter length of developmental period was recorded on Kwankwasiya (40 days) (Table 1). The difference in length of developmental period between the cultivars was small but significant. This is in contrast to findings by Ghorpade *et al.* (1998) who studied the relative susceptibility of seven groundnut cultivars to pod borer, *C. serrate* in storage. They reported shortest developmental period (66.22 days) in

SB-11 and maximum in RVB-1 (98.17 days). These inherent responses of cowpea varieties to infestations have been shown related to differences in some morphological, physical and chemical factors (Singh, 2005).

The dynamics of emergence of adult *T. castaneum* F_1 progeny on five groundnut substrates were presented in Figure 1. Analysis of the figure indicated that adults emerged earlier, 22 DAI (days after infestation) on Yar-dakar cultivar. First F_1 adult emergence on other cultivars was recorded two days later. Period of emergence on Kwankwasiya was shorter than the other varieties and lasted 40 days compared to 44 days on Yar-dakar, Kampala and Gwandara with the longest days (44 DAI) while, complete adult emergence recorded on Yar-baino is 42 days. According to Medugu *et al.* (2021) who observed the differences among cowpea varieties with respect to F_1 progeny production, median developmental time and ultimately, the susceptibility index, noted that variations in the resistance of cowpea varieties indicated the inherent abilities of each variety to resist *C. maculatus* infestation.

The cumulative daily emergence curve of *T. castaneum* is shown in Figure 2. Throughout the period of adult emergence, higher number of adults emerged on Yar-dakar and Gwandara followed by Yar-baino and Kampala and lowest on Kwankwasiya. Gofishu and Belete, (2014) noted that progeny emergence was highly correlated with the susceptibility of varieties to insect infestation. The current study meanwhile shows that, as the MDT increases, the F_1 progeny emergence decreases. It was also observed that, a shorter MDT gives rise to more F_1 progeny and the greater is the susceptibility index of the cultivar and that the SI is inversely related to MDT with the number of F_1 progeny showing a positive relationship with the SI.

Figure 1: The dynamics of progeny emergence of *T. castaneum* on five groundnut varieties under laboratory conditions

Figure 2: The Cumulative emergence curves of *T. castaneum* on five groundnut varieties under laboratory conditions

Susceptibility of Five Groundnut Cultivars to *T. castaneum* Infestation

The groundnut cultivars' susceptibility indices to *T. castaneum* infection were not substantially different ($p \geq 0.05$). The moderate resistance of the five groundnut cultivars to *T. castaneum* was not significantly different among them (Table 2). According to Table 2, this susceptibility status demonstrated that the SI and MDT have an antagonistic relationship. The SI and the quantity of F_1 descendants, however, were positively correlated (Table 2). In this study, it was found that the feeding substrate affects a wide range of insect life history characteristics, including fertility, developmental time, and lifespan. According

to research by Hasansab et al. (2009), there were significant variances across groundnut types in their SI to bruchid infestation. This implies that Gwandara and Yar-dakar cultivars could be damaged by *T. castaneum* when infestation occurs in store, leading to a rapid buildup of population. However, cracks in the pods developed during drying and handling also boosts the susceptibility to pest attack (Nautiyal, 2002) as observed in this study by *T. castaneum* which happened to be a primary pest. In addition, Kwankwasiya cultivar appears to be not very supportive of *T. castaneum* indicating relative fewer progeny and shorter developmental period. Abebe, et al. (2009) showed that, the index of

susceptibility is hinged on the assumption that the more number of F_1 progeny produced within shorter duration, the more susceptible the grains.

Percentage Grain Damage and Weight Loss caused by *T. castaneum* Infestation on five Groundnut Cultivars

Grain damage and weight loss is the result of damage caused by the partial or complete consumption of the groundnut (Plate II). These losses are mostly caused by the tunneling and feeding activities of the larvae rather than the adults. Evoldo *et al.* (2017) stated that based on the type of destruction caused by *T. castaneum* in Brazil nut, this insect may be classified, for this product, as a pest capable of generating quantitative and qualitative damage. The results of this study showed that there are no significant differences in the mean percentage grain damaged due to the activities of *T. castaneum* among the groundnut cultivars (Table II). The damage caused by *T. castaneum* over 60 days storage period was generally low and ranged from 6.72 - 11.83%. Kampala cultivar showed significant difference between the cultivars which suffered lowest level of grain damage (6.72%). The highest grain damage was recorded on Yar-dakar cultivar of 11.83%. Kwankwasiya, Gwandara and Yar-baino cultivars has percentages grain damage of 10.45 %, 9.30 % and 8.35 %, respectively. Grain damage of groundnut due to tunneling has an important commercial implication. This coupled with losses in weight is a substantial commercial loss. In addition to these losses, infestation by insects can cause mould development, loss in nutritional and aneastatic values. It is imperative that groundnut sellers are aware of the economic implication of insect infestation of groundnut. This research is in agreement to the findings by Baoua *et al.*

(2015) and Baributsa *et al.* (2017) who indicated that estimated storage weight losses in Niger ranged from 8 - 14% after 6 to 7 months of storage and this ratio is quite low compared to that recorded on cowpea, which varies from 66 - 70% after 5 months of storage (Baoua *et al.*, 2015)

In terms of grain weight loss, there are no significant differences ($P < 0.005$) in the mean percentage weight losses due to the activity of *T. castaneum* among the groundnut cultivars (Table 2; Plate 2). Kampala and Kwankwasiya cultivars showed significant difference ($P < 0.005$) in weight loss by the activity of *T. castaneum* of 7.50 % and 6.25 %, respectively, lower than half the loss sustained by Yar-dakar, Yar-baino and Gwandara of 19.96 %, 15.26 % and 16.65 % (Table II). Lowest weight losses recorded by Kampala and Kwankwasiya cultivars may be attributed to inherent qualities that make it less susceptible to damage by *T. castaneum*. Attack by *T. castaneum* caused evident loss of dry matter resulting in losses of bulk mass, concurring with problems associated with pest attack in other stored grains (Caneppele *et al.*, 2003). This Highest weight loss from this study is not in conformity to the findings of Oaya *et al.* (2012) who found out that in Nigeria, weight losses of groundnuts are even higher and estimated to be around 70 % and 68 % for shelled and unshelled groundnuts, respectively. The scoring of all parameters confirms that Yar-dakar was the most susceptible groundnut cultivar to infestation by this insect pest. This was followed by Yar-baino and Gwandara, while Kwankwasiya and Kampala were the least susceptible groundnut cultivars. It can be safely concluded that Yar-dakar cultivar is most susceptible to infestation.

However, it was observed that the extensive boring behavior of the larvae of *T. castaneum* caused damage and consequently resulted in loss (Plate II). The difference in the high infestation levels observed in Yar-dakar, Yar-baino and Gwandara as compared to Kwankwasiya and Kampala could be attributed to the size, composition and the texture of the groundnut, which makes them favorable to infestation. Host substrate preference might have also played an important role. Though, all the groundnut cultivars were

moderately resistant to *T. castaneum*, this was authenticated by some authors who showed that antibiosis and non-preference worked as mechanisms of resistance in stored grains (Chuck-Hernández *et al.*, 2013). Hence, the level of damage during storage depends on the number of emerging adults and the duration of the developmental time. Therefore, cultivars favouring faster and more adult emergence will suffer more damaged.

Table 1 Effects of groundnut varieties on some life history characters of *T. castaneum*

Varieties	Life history parameter			
	F 1 progeny	LDP (days)	SI	SS
Gwandara	15.10 ± 0.26 ^{ab}	44.0 ± 5.49 ^a	5.36 ± 0.16 ^a	MR
Kampala	12.15 ± 0.30 ^{ab}	44.0 ± 5.49 ^a	4.93 ± 0.16 ^{ab}	MR
Kwankwasiya	9.01 ± 0.28 ^{ab}	40.0 ± 5.49 ^a	4.77 ± 0.15 ^{ab}	MR
Yar -baino	12.85 ± 0.23 ^{ab}	42.0 ± 5.49 ^a	5.28 ± 0.16 ^a	MR
Yar -dakara	18.35 ± 0.37 ^{ab}	44.0 ± 5.49 ^a	5.74 ± 0.21 ^a	MR

Means followed by the same letter(s) within a column are not significantly different according to Tukey - Kramer HSD test at 5% level of probability.

LDP = Length of developmental period; **SI** = Susceptibility index; **SS** = Susceptibility status; **MR** = moderately resistant.

Table 2 Percent grain damage and weight loss of five groundnut varieties caused by *T. castaneum*

Varieties	Grain damage (%)	Weight loss (%)
Gwandara	9.30 ± 3.95 ^a	16.65 ± 5.4 ^{ab}
Kampala	6.72 ± 6.10 ^b	6.25 ± 2.39 ^c
Kwankwasiya	10.45 ± 1.92 ^a	7.50 ± 2.50 ^c
Yar -baino	8.35 ± 2.1 ^a	15.26 ± 5.49 ^{ab}
Yar -dakara	11.83 ± 1.24 ^a	19.96 ± 9.37 ^a

Means followed by the same letter(s) within a column are not significantly different according to Tukey - Kramer HSD test at 5% level of probability

Plate II: Samples of damaged groundnut cultivars due to *T. castaneum* infestation

CONCLUSION

The study revealed that According to the report, *T. castaneum* is quickly emerging as a significant primary groundnut pest. However, this insect only has a mild infestation. According to laboratory research, *T. castaneum* life cycle characteristics, including the number of offspring and length of the developmental period, are influenced by the type of groundnut substrate. The Yar-dakar cultivar of groundnuts has the most weight loss and grain damage over a 60-day storage period, making it the most susceptible. The cultivars Kampala and Kwankwasiya saw the least weight loss and grain damage as a result

of this insect. All groundnut cultivars are vulnerable to *T. castaneum* attacks, and it can successfully reproduce there. Therefore, this study gives information on the likelihood that *T. castaneum* may become a primary groundnut pest.

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